

The interrelationship between clinical and immunity variables in epilepsy

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SUMMARY

Introduction. The role of cellular immunity in the pathogenesis of epilepsy, as an interaction between immunity and clinical and neurobiological variables is not properly understood.

Aim. The aim of the current study was to investigate the possible relationship between epilepsy forms, gender, focus localization, lateralization, handedness and cellular immunity with seizures frequency, their severity and length of therapeutic remission in partial forms of epilepsy.

Material and methods. Ninety two patients (38 men and 54 women) were included in the study. Symptomatic epilepsy was diagnosed in 40 patients and the cryptogenic form was diagnosed in 52 patients. The amount of different lymphocyte clusters were evaluated and they were transformed into nominal variables for MANOVA analysis. MANOVA was used for the analysis of the interrelationship between nominal fixed factors (epilepsy forms, gender, handedness, and focus laterality, and immunity variables) and dependent variables (remission and seizure frequency and their severity).

Results. Simple partial seizure (SPS) and complex partial seizure (CPS) frequencies were under the influence of interaction between immune and neurobiological variables. SPS, and in particular sensory SPS, were associated with CD4/CD8 ratio, gender, left temporal focus and handedness. The highest frequencies of SPS were revealed in cases of low CD4/CD8 ratio combined with left temporal focus, female gender and left-handedness. The maximal CPS frequency was observed in patients with a left frontal focus combined with a high B-lymphocyte level. The more severe seizures were revealed in left-handers with low CD8 and high CD4/CD8 ratio and in frontal left focus and a high T-lymphocyte level. There was a correlation between CD4 cell level and length of remission.

Conclusion. The complex multifarious connections between neurobiological, immune and clinical variables in patients with partial forms of epilepsy really exist.

Key words: temporal lobe epilepsy • frontal lobe epilepsy • gender • right-handedness • left-handedness • immunity variables • focus laterality • length of remission • seizure severity

INTRODUCTION

Psychoneuroimmunology represents a relatively new integrated science based on several medical disciplines, including immunology, neurology and psychiatry. The principal aim of this discipline concerns the study of interaction between immunological activity and neu-

rological and mental processes. The term *psychoneuroimmunology* itself was first coined by Robert Ader in 1980, and since then a great deal of research studies have been performed (Ader, 1980; Daruna, 2004; Vedarhara and Irvin, 2005). Nevertheless, the data on psy-

choneuroimmunology of epilepsy are rather scarce and concern mostly the problems of humoral immunity.

Thus, a suggestion has been made, that the autoimmune nature of some epilepsies came from the presence of antibodies to a major excitatory neurotransmitter in the CNS and data on association between epilepsy and certain autoimmune diseases such as systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), antiphospholipid syndrome and stiff person syndrome, as a whole, confirms this suggestion (Aarli, 2000; Palace and Lang, 2000; Levite, 2002).

Moreover, some cases of epilepsy are associated with primary IgA (and occasionally IgG) deficiency. The IgA deficiency state was apparently reversible, since normalization of serum levels occurred after withdrawal of phenytoin. Mean serum IgG was lower in epileptic patients who had taken phenytoin for less than 1 year and had a low IgA, than in patients who had taken phenytoin for 19 years or more. At present the pathogenesis of some CNS disorders seems to be associated with autoantibodies production, and possibility exists that epilepsy represents the first manifestation of the autoimmune syndrome itself, since the antibodies themselves are thought to be directly implicated in causing epilepsy (Palace and Lang, 2000; Levite and Rhart, 2000).

Clinical and experimental data suggest that both innate and adaptive (acquired) immunity may be involved in epilepsy pathogenesis (Orozco-Suarez et al., 2012). Innate immune mechanisms represent an immediate and nonspecific host response against pathogens via activation of resident cerebral immune cells and inflammatory mediators. On the other hand, adaptive immunity includes activation of antigen specific B- and T-lymphocytes and antibodies to concrete antigens in the context of viral infection and autoimmune disorders (Daruna, 2004; Vedhara and Irvin, 2005; Orozco-Suarez et al., 2012).

All these data are interpreted in terms that epilepsy pathogenesis may represent in some way an inflammatory process in the brain (Aarli, 2000; Aronica and Crino, 2011), and so-called Rasmussen's encephalitis confirms this suggestion (Rasmussen and Anderman, 1989; Rogers et al., 1994).

Nevertheless, the role of inflammation in the pathogenesis of other forms of epilepsy has not been elucidated properly yet and much less is known about cellular immunity in epilepsy. Moreover, the data on the state of cellular immune mechanisms in epilepsy are practically absent and had not drawn a decent attention of

investigators, although such data might help to understand the pathogenesis of epilepsy more thoroughly.

It must be emphasised, that since the studies of Geschwind and coauthors (Geschwind and Behan, 1982; Geschwind and Galaburda, 1985a,b,c) the handedness is regarded as a principal functional characteristic of cerebral organization and depends on immune and hormonal mechanisms. Moreover, the authors have shown that certain autoimmune diseases are prevalent in left-handers over the right-handed persons (Geschwind and Behan, 1982; Geschwind and Galaburda, 1985a,b,c; McManus and Bryden, 1991). It implies the intrinsic relations between immunity and cerebral lateralization, and handedness, in particular, although the role of handedness in terms of interaction with immunity in epilepsy has yet to be elucidated.

In our previous studies the role of cerebral lateralization with emphasis on handedness in predicting of comorbid psychopathological disorders has been shown (Kalinin et al., 2010; 2012; 2013). Along with these data the role of focus localization and lateralization in the partial epilepsy forms has been established, and interaction between gender, epilepsy form, focus laterality and handedness was important for prediction of remission length and seizures reduction (Kalinin et al., 2013).

In this context suggestion can be made that handedness in epileptic patients *a priori* may be associated with immune mechanisms too, since the pathogenesis of epilepsy is thought to be based on multiple interaction between immunity, neurobiological and clinical variable.

All these data *a priori* could help to understand the pathogenesis of epilepsy more properly with emphasis on interaction between neurology and immunity. Many problems in this context remain without adequate answers. Thus, whether there really exist any relationship between seizures of different semiotics on the one hand and immune variables, on the other hand? Besides, what is the possible relationship between immune variables, remission and handedness in patients with epilepsy?

AIM

The current pilot study was designed and performed in order to identify the possible relationship between cellular immune variables and clinical data in patients with partial forms of epilepsy

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The main characteristics of the studied patients are included in table 1. The study comprised of 92 inpatients

Table 1. The main patient characteristics

Number of patients	92
Gender	Male – 38 Female – 54
Age (years, mean \pm SD)	32.1 \pm 9.8
Seizure onset (years, mean \pm SD)	16.6 \pm 12.9
Duration of epilepsy (years, mean \pm SD)	15.2 \pm 9.7
Type of epilepsy	
Frontal lobe, n (%)	16 (17.4%)
Temporal lobe, n (%)	36 (39.1%)
Multifocal, n (%)	40 (43.5%)
Form of epilepsy	
Cryptogenic, n (%)	50 (54.3%)
Symptomatic, n (%)	42 (45.7%)
Focus laterality (EEG studies)	
Left-sided focus	32 (34.8%)
Right-sided focus	30 (32.6%)
Bilateral foci	30 (32.6%)

(38 men, 54 women) with epilepsy, that were admitted into the Department of Brain Organic Disorders and Epilepsy in 2013–2016 years. In 40 patients, the diagnosis of symptomatic epilepsy was made whilst the diagnosis of cryptogenic epilepsy was made in 52 patients. All patients had undergone a MRI-scanning, and the final conclusion on symptomatic epilepsy has been done after MRI-scanning. In most cases (37 patients) mesial temporal sclerosis was observed, while in 3 patients intra-cerebral cysts were detected.

In each patient, following EEG features were taken into consideration, to detect the localization and laterality of the epileptic focus (foci): slow background activity, spike and/or sharp waves, spike and slow wave complexes and sharp and slow wave complexes. All clinical and EEG characteristics are listed in table 1.

The EEG was recorded during twenty four hours for each patient.

Temporal-lobe epilepsy was diagnosed in 36 patients, frontal-lobe epilepsy in 16 patients and temporal-frontal epilepsy was diagnosed in 40 patients. The term “temporal-frontal epilepsy” in the present study was used in those patients in which epileptic bursts were registered both the temporal and frontal regions of brain.

The focus laterality was detected by a visual EEG-method (interictal and ictal EEG analysis during diurnal and night monitoring).

Left-sided foci were detected in 32 patients whilst right-sided foci were detected in 30 patients and bilateral foci in 30 patients. In the present study seizures were classified in accordance with guidelines of the International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE), 1981.

These guidelines are still used in Russia, while the recent ILAE guidelines, 2010 have not been validated yet for general use. Thus simple partial seizures (SPS), complex partial seizures (CPS) and secondary generalized seizures (SGS) were defined in accordance with the ILAE, (1981) guidelines.

Data on frequency of each seizure semiotics and the length of seizure-free periods have been obtained from patient diaries. In this context the mean number of each seizure type per month has been calculated for the last six months and the length of remission (the full control of seizures) in the months preceding their admittance to hospital has been included into the statistical analysis. The mean length of seizure control was 3.4 \pm 8.5 months and varied 0–48 months.

An assessment of seizures severity was undertaken according to the National Hospital Seizure Severity Scale (NHS3) (O’Donoghue et al., 1996).

In addition, the assessment of handedness Annett’s scale was used (Annett, 1970). Persons, whose global score on this scale was lower than – 5 points were regarded as left-handers, while persons with global score exceeded +5 points – as right-handers. Among all studied patients 85 were considered as right-handers (Mean \pm Std. Dev.: +21.9 \pm 2.7) whilst 7 patients were classified as left-handers (Mean \pm Std. Dev.: –9.9 \pm 12.9).

Blood samples were obtained from every patient after being admitted to hospital. The analyses was performed on cytofluorimeter FC 500 instrument (Beckman Coulter).

The number of different lymphocytes clusters were calculated. Among them the number of T-lym-

Table 2. The mean and median values of the various immunological variables

Immunological variable	Mean \pm SD	Median	Range of variable
T-lymphocytes (CD3+)	74.2 \pm 6.5	74.4	55.4–86.9
T-helpers (CD3+CD4+)	46.6 \pm 6.8	47.6	31.7–51.4
T-suppressors (CD3+CD8+)	25.9 \pm 6.3	25.7	12.9–42.8
T-lymphocytes - NK (CD3+CD16+56+)	6.3 \pm 4.4	4.8	0.7–19.4
B-lymphocytes (CD3-CD19+)	12.4 \pm 4.9	12.0	5.0–32.3
Natural Killers (NK) (CD3-CD16+CD56+)	11.5 \pm 5.5	11.1	3.4–32.3
Regulatory Index (CD4/CD8 ratio)	2.0 \pm 0.7	1.9	0.7–3.7

phocytes (CD3+), T-helpers (CD3+CD4+), T-cytotoxic (CD3+CD8+), T-NK (CD3+CD16+CD56+), B-lymphocytes (CD3+CD19+), Natural Killers (CD3-CD16+CD+56) and regulatory index (CD4/CD8 ratio) were analyzed.

Ethical Committee

The design of the current study was approved by the Local Ethical Committee of the Moscow Research Institute of Psychiatry, Ministry of Healthcare, Russian Federation.

Statistics

The MANOVA-statistics was used for analysis of the interrelationship between nominal independent variables (fixed factors) and dependent quantitative variables. MANOVA represents a variant of multivariate analysis, which is widely used for the assessment of influence of certain nominal variables (fixed factors) upon variance of quantitative dependent variables. That analysis, estimating the variance, allows a single simultaneous comparison for three or more groups. The result becomes a type of screening test that indicates whether at least one group differs significantly from the others (Feinstein, 2002; Mathews and Farewell, 2007).

Besides, the interrelationship between nominal fixed factors its influence upon dependent variables may also be revealed. The choice of MANOVA was based on the fact that this test has many advantages in comparison with widely used t test or z test although each of them is designed to find the possible differences between compared groups. MANOVA is a much more sensitive method compared to that of the t test and is able to reveal existed differences between groups when t test

cannot detect them (Feinstein, 2002; Mathews, 2007).

The variables of gender, epilepsy form, handedness and focus lateralization were selected as independent factors.

In addition, for the purpose of MANOVA, all immune quantitative variables were transformed into nominal ones. For this purpose variables of T-lymphocytes (CD3+), T-helpers (CD3+CD4+), T-cytotoxic (CD3+CD8+), T-NK (CD3+CD16+CD56+), B-lymphocytes (CD3+CD19+) and Natural Killers (CD3-CD16+CD+56) the median was defined. Consequently it was possible to separate patients into groups with low (below median) and high (above median) variable level.

The variable of CD4/CD8 ratio was divided into three categories in line with special recommendations implying low or immune deficiency (< 1.5), normal (1.5–2.5) and high (> 2.5) level of immune regulatory index (Amadori et al., 1995; Birnbaum, 1998; Daruna, 2004; Vedhara and Irvin, 2005).

The median and mean values of the studied immune variables are listed in table 2.

The length of remission, seizures frequencies and seizures severity were considered as dependent variables. In the present study any intentional selection of certain variables for analysis purpose was avoided. A priori hypothesis was that certain interrelationship between gender, handedness, epilepsies form and focus laterality and immune variables on one hand, and variables of remission and seizures frequencies, on the other hand should exist.

At the final step of study the mean values of remission length and seizures frequencies for different combinations of epilepsy forms, immune variables, gender, handedness and focus laterality were calculated, and

Table 3. Results of MANOVA. The Influence of interaction of different factors, including immunological and neurobiological variables, on frequency of seizures, their severity and remission length (Significance “p” and Strength of influence “ η^2 ”)

Variables & their interaction	Sensory partial seizures	Complex partial seizures	Secondary generalized seizures	Severity of seizures (NHS3)	Remission length (months)
Gender* CD4/CD8	p=0.013 $\eta^2=0.116$	p=0.938 $\eta^2=0.002$	p=0.7 $\eta^2=0.009$	p=0.832 $\eta^2=0.005$	p=0.632 $\eta^2=0.012$
Gender*CD8	p=0.046 $\eta^2=0.054$	p=0.100 $\eta^2=0.034$	p=0.981 $\eta^2=0.000$	p=0.740 $\eta^2=0.001$	p=0.233 $\eta^2=0.018$
TL* CD4/CD8	p=0.023 $\eta^2=0.097$	p=0.288 $\eta^2=0.032$	p=0.505 $\eta^2=0.018$	p=0.318 $\eta^2=0.029$	p=0.918 $\eta^2=0.002$
TR*CD4/CD8	p=0.019 $\eta^2=0.102$	p=0.268 $\eta^2=0.034$	p=0.065 $\eta^2=0.068$	p=0.438 $\eta^2=0.021$	p=0.759 $\eta^2=0.007$
FL* B-lymphocytes	p=0.150 $\eta^2=0.027$	p=0.040 $\eta^2=0.052$	p=0.817 $\eta^2=0.001$	p=0.689 $\eta^2=0.002$	p=0.573 $\eta^2=0.004$
FR* B-lymphocytes	p=0.685 $\eta^2=0.002$	p=0.503 $\eta^2=0.06$	p=0.531 $\eta^2=0.005$	p=0.749 $\eta^2=0.001$	p=0.689 $\eta^2=0.002$
FL* T-lymphocytes	p=0.223 $\eta^2=0.019$	p=0.343 $\eta^2=0.011$	p=0.006 $\eta^2=0.093$	p=0.029 $\eta^2=0.057$	p=0.077 $\eta^2=0.038$
FR* T-lymphocytes	p=0.800 $\eta^2=0.001$	p=0.788 $\eta^2=0.001$	p=0.873 $\eta^2=0.000$	p=0.023 $\eta^2=0.063$	p=0.432 $\eta^2=0.008$
CD4	p=0.259 $\eta^2=0.016$	p=0.739 $\eta^2=0.001$	p=0.892 $\eta^2=0.000$	p=0.07 $\eta^2=0.038$	p=0.006 $\eta^2=0.089$
FL*NK	p=0.563 $\eta^2=0.004$	p=0.834 $\eta^2=0.001$	p=0.011 $\eta^2=0.078$	p=0.049 $\eta^2=0.047$	p=0.018 $\eta^2=0.068$
FR*NK	p=0.870 $\eta^2=0.000$	p=0.462 $\eta^2=0.007$	p=0.960 $\eta^2=0.000$	p=0.145 $\eta^2=0.026$	p=0.608 $\eta^2=0.003$
Hand*CD4	p=0.000 $\eta^2=0.333$	P=0.639 $\eta^2=0.003$	p=0.396 $\eta^2=0.009$	p=0.057 $\eta^2=0.044$	p=0.925 $\eta^2=0.000$
Hand*CD8	p=0.000 $\eta^2=0.183$	P=0.739 $\eta^2=0.001$	p=0.489 $\eta^2=0.006$	p=0.048 $\eta^2=0.048$	p=0.548 $\eta^2=0.004$
Hand*CD4/CD8	p=0.000 $\eta^2=0.341$	P=0.384 $\eta^2=0.025$	p=0.219 $\eta^2=0.039$	p=0.017 $\eta^2=0.098$	p=0.939 $\eta^2=0.002$
Hand*NK	p=0.000 $\eta^2=0.200$	P=0.821 $\eta^2=0.001$	p=0.619 $\eta^2=0.003$	p=0.762 $\eta^2=0.001$	p=0.277 $\eta^2=0.015$

TL – temporal left focus; TR – temporal right focus; FL – frontal left focus; FR – frontal right focus; NK – natural killers; Hand – handedness; * – interaction (combination) between variables

comparisons were made between them. The combinations which caused the maximal level for remission length and minimal in seizures frequencies were regarded as favorable. In contrast, the combinations with the lowest values for remission and high for the seizures frequencies were considered as unfavorable.

RESULTS

The principal data are shown in tables 3 and 4. In table 3 the data on influence of immune variables in combination with other neurobiological variables (gender, focus laterality and handedness) on seizures frequencies, their severity and remission length, are presented.

As can be seen, the statistically significant effect on seizures frequency, their severity and remission dura-

tion was observed under interaction (combination) of immune and neurobiological variables, and only isolated CD4 variable has significant influence on remission length. Noteworthy, the term “interaction” here must be understood strictly as statistical, but not physiological one, but it implies relationships between immunological and neurobiological variables.

Table 4 shows the logical sequence of table 3 and contents the mean values of stochastically significant discrepancies of compared variables. The compared data of pairs related to statistically significant influence of immune and neurobiological variables on dependent variables of seizures, their severity and remission length are presented, while the other statistically non-significant data are not included.

Table 4. Results of MANOVA. The mean values of different seizure frequency, their severity and remission duration under influence of different combinations of neurobiological and immunological factors

Variables & their interaction	Sensory partial seizures	Complex partial seizures	Secondary generalized seizures	Severity of seizures (NHS3)	Remission length (months)
FG*CD4/CD8 Low vs. FG*CD4/CD8 Normal	155.4 ± 255.3 (n=8) vs. 22.8 ± 56.8 (n=29) p=0.006	-	-	-	-
FG*CD4/CD8 Low vs. MG*CD4/CD8 Low	155.4 ± 255.3 (n=8) vs. 4.2 ± 11.3 (n=16) p=0.039	-	-	-	-
Temp L* CD4/CD8 low vs. Temp R* CD4/CD8 low	150 ± 275 (n=7) vs. 3.25 ± 10.3 (n=12) p=0.038	-	-	-	-
Temp L* CD4/CD8 low vs. Temp L* CD4/CD8 normal	150 ± 275 (n=7) vs. 27.3 ± 68.7 (n=26) p=0.021	-	-	-	-
Temp R* CD4/CD8 low vs. Temp R* CD4/CD8 normal	3.3 ± 10.3 (n=12) vs. 18.3 ± 28.0 (n=15) p=0.045	-	-	-	-
Fr L*B-lymph. Low vs. Fr L*B-lymph. High	-	4.1 ± 12.5 (n=16) vs. 26.9 ± 50.2 (n=16) p=0.044	-	-	-
Fr L*T-lymph. Low vs. Fr L*T-lymph. High	-	-	13.6 ± 18.5 (n=17) vs. 23.7 ± 31.1 (n=15) n.s.	10.8 ± 7.7 (n=18) vs. 15.3 ± 7.4 (n=15) p=0.048	4.9 ± 12.5 (n=18) vs. 1.9 ± 6.2 (n=15) n.s.
Fr R*T-lymph. Low vs. Fr R*T-lymph. High	-	-	-	11.3 ± 9.4 (n=14) vs. 16.4 ± 8.0 (n=17) p=0.058	2.1 ± 6.4 (n=14) vs. 1.5 ± 2.9 (n=17) n.s.
CD4 Low vs. CD4 High	-	-	-	-	0.7 ± 2.1 (n=40) vs. 5.8 ± 11.1 (n=45) p=0.0054
Fr L*NK Low vs. Fr L*NK High	-	-	22.9 ± 29.2 (n=19) vs. 11.6 ± 17.2 (n=14) n.s.	14.2 ± 8.2 (n=19) vs. 11.1 ± 7.1 (n=14) n.s.	1.5 ± 5.5 (n=19) vs. 6.3 ± 14.0 (n=14) p=0.09
FR R*NK Low vs. FR R*NK High	-	-	-	11.3 ± 8.4 (n=25) vs. 16.2 ± 10.5 (n=27) p=0.035	-
Fr L*NK Low vs. Fr R*NK Low	-	-	22.9 ± 29.2 (n=19) vs. 5.4 ± 10.7 (n=26) p=0.007	14.2 ± 8.2 (n=19) vs. 14.8 ± 8.8 (n=18) n.s.	5.5 ± 9.5 (n=25) vs. 1.5 ± 5.5 (n=19) p=0.055
Left H.*CD4 low vs. Right H.*CD4 low	351.3 ± 348 (n=3) vs. 20.8 ± 61.4 (n=33) p=0.0001	-	-	-	-

Variables & their interaction	Sensory partial seizures	Complex partial seizures	Secondary generalized seizures	Severity of seizures (NHS3)	Remission length (months)
Left H.*CD4 low vs. Left H.*CD4 high	351.3 ± 348 (n=3) vs. 7.25 ± 11.4 (n=4) p=0.048	-	-	-	-
Left H.*CD8 Low vs. Right H.*CD8 Low	-	-	-	24.7 ± 11.6 (n=3) vs. 13.0 ± 9.4 (n=39) p=0.023	-
Left H.*CD4/ CD8 Low vs. Right H.* CD4/ CD8 Low	350 ± 350 (n=3) vs. 2.4 ± 9.0 (n=16) p=0.0003	-	-	-	-
Left H.*CD4/ CD8 High vs. Right H.* CD4/ CD8 High	-	-	-	38.0 ± 0 (n=1) vs. 12.50 ± 11.4 (n=12) p=0.005	-
Left H.*NK low vs. Right H.*NK low	262.5 ± 335 (n=4) vs. 8.0 ± 20.4 (n=37) p=0.00001	-	-	-	-
Right H.NK low vs. Right H.*NK high	8.0 ± 20.4 (n=37) vs. 23.1,0 ± 61.3 (n=36) p=0.08	-	-	-	-

TL – temporal left focus; TR – temporal right focus; FL- frontal left focus; FR – frontal right focus; CD4 – T-helpers; CD8 – T-suppressors; CD4/CD8 – regulatory index; NK – natural killers; Left H.– left-handedness; Right H. – right-handedness; FG – female gender; MG – male gender; * – interaction (combination) between variables. Only the means with statistically significant discrepancies and trends to discrepancies are included in the table.

As can be seen, the high frequency of SPS was obtained as a result of interaction of gender and regulatory index (CD4/CD8 ratio), and female gender interacting with low CD4/CD8 index resulted in maximal SPS frequency, while in cases with normal CD4/CD8 ratio the SPS amount was much less frequent ($p = 0.006$).

The comparison of females and males with low CD4/CD8 ratio revealed the maximal SPS frequency in women and minimal frequency in men ($p = 0.039$). For normal and high levels of CD4/CD8 ratio, such gender discrepancies were not observed.

Similarly, within the female group a significant discrepancy existed between low and high CD8 cells level, and higher SPS frequency was observed in a subgroup with higher level of CD8-cells. These discrepancy were not observed in men.

In addition, the maximal frequency of SPS was revealed under the influence of interaction of CD4/C8 ratio and the left temporal focus, while interaction of CD4/CD8 ratio with the right focus results in mini-

mal frequency of SPS. Accordingly statistically significant discrepancies were observed between low and normal CD4/CD8 index for the left temporal focus (with maximal value of SPS frequency for low CD4/CD8 ratio) and for the right temporal focus (with higher SPS frequency for normal CD4/CD8 ratio). In other words, the so-called reciprocal relationships do exist between the left and the right foci in terms of their influence upon SPS frequency under interaction with low or higher CD4/CD8 ratio.

Noteworthy, there was no statistically significant influence on CPS and SGS under interaction of CD4/CD8 level and temporal focus.

On the other hand, the frequency of CPS depended on interaction of frontal left focus with B-lymphocyte level, and higher CPS frequency was obtained for high B-lymphocyte level compared with low B-lymphocyte level.

The interaction of frontal left focus with T-lymphocyte level had effect on severity of seizures (NHS3), and

more severe seizures were revealed in case of high T-lymphocytes level compared with low T-lymphocyte level, while for the right frontal focus only a trend to the interaction with T-lymphocyte level was observed, and a tendency to more severe seizures was observed in cases with a high T-lymphocyte level.

Principally, that handedness and CD4/CD8 ratio had also an influence on SPS frequency and severity of seizures. The maximal frequency of SPS was revealed in left-handed patients with low a CD4/CD8 ratio in comparison with right-handed persons with a low regulatory index.

On the other hand, the highest level of severity was obtained under interaction of left-handedness and high level of CD4/CD8 ratio, while in the cases of right-handedness the severity of seizures was much lower ($p=0.005$).

Remission length depended strictly on the isolated CD4 variable and interaction between frontal left focus and NK level. However, only the isolated CD4 variable has significant effect upon remission length, and longer remissions were observed in cases of high level of CD4 cells ($p=0.005$), while the interaction of left frontal focus with a high level of NK cells resulted only in a trend to more prolonged remission ($p=0.09$).

Handedness seems to be a principal item which exerts interaction with several immune variables and by that can also influence the frequency of SPS and severity of seizures. Thus, the maximal SPS frequency was observed in left-handed patients compared with right-handed patients with a low level of CD4 cells. Besides, the maximal SPS frequency was obtained in left-handed persons with a low level of CD4 cells compared with left-handed persons with a high level of CD4 cells.

In contrast, the interaction between handedness and NK cells level has been revealed in their influence on the frequency of SPS, and the maximal amount of SPS was observed in the left-handed patients with low content of NK cells, while in right-handed patients with low content of NK cells was registered with much less SPS frequency ($p=0.00001$). Additionally a trend to higher SPS frequency in right-handed persons with higher amount of NK cells was observed ($p=0.08$).

DISCUSSION

The present study is the first to study the connection between variables of cellular immunity with frequency of different types of seizures, their severity and remission length in patients with partial forms of epilep-

sy. Noteworthy, some additional neurobiological criteria were also used in order to identify any relationships with immune, clinical and neurobiological variables.

The study has some shortcomings. Thus, only 3 seizure types of partial epilepsies were included in the study, while the seizures of other semiotics were beyond the scope of trial. It should also be emphasized, that in the present study the primary focus of investigation entailed patients with partial epilepsies, since these seizure types represent the most frequent diagnostic categories in epileptology, and simple partial, complex partial and secondary generalized seizures are thought to represent the main seizure kinds of partial forms of epilepsy.

Moreover, the distinct localization and lateralization of the focus in partial seizure types allows the possibility to relate certain clinical, neurobiological and immune parameters with discrete brain structures that can help to enhance our understanding of the pathogenesis of epilepsy.

The principal findings of the present study relate to the existence of multiple interrelationships between immunity, neurobiological variables and some clinical signs. Also, we observed that SPS and to less a degree CPS are under the influence of interaction between immune and neurobiological variables.

Frequency and remission of simple partial seizures

Thus, the frequency of SPS depends on the interaction between CD4/CD8 ratio, CD8 cells level and gender, temporal lobe epilepsy with left sided focus and left-handedness. Noteworthy, all the above highlighted neurobiological variables caused a high frequency of SPS under condition of low levels of CD4/CD8 ratio, while in the cases of normal levels of this ratio the low frequency of SPS was observed. In other words, the normal values of CD4/CD8 index are a prerequisite of SPS frequency reduction, and thus seems to be an indicator of their reduction, while the low values, in contrast, are an indicator of persistence of SPS. Interestingly, that high values of CD4/CD8 ratio (>2.5) as a rule have no connection with SPS frequency irrespective of focus lateralization and localization, handedness and gender. It implies the principal role of normal immune activity that seems to be *conditio sine qua non* for the low SPS frequency.

Principally, that male gender, temporal lobe epilepsy with the right focus and right-handedness under low level of CD4/CD8 index caused the low frequency of

SPS, and thus may be regarded as a prognostic favorable in terms of SPS frequency reduction.

It should be emphasized that in our previous studies the unfavorable role of female gender and alexithymia in terms of remission had been reported, and in this context the results presented in this study are in accordance with previous results (Kalinin et al., 2010; 2012; 2013).

Interestingly, that remission length (the control over all seizures) depends on the CD4 cells level, which are regarded as T-helpers among lymphocytes and sustain the state of active immunity (Amadori et al., 1995; Birnbaum, 1998; Daruna, 2004; Vedhara and Irvin, 2005). Obviously, it corresponds to high level of regulatory D4/D8 ratio and it implies the anticonvulsive properties of this ratio, directed strictly to SPS low frequency.

Frequency and remission of complex partial seizures

CPS, on the other hand, are under the influence of interaction between frontal left focus and B-lymphocytes level. The low level of B-lymphocytes seems to be a prerequisite of low CPS frequency and thus has favorable prognostic significance, while the high level of B-lymphocytes correlates with high CPS frequency and consequently has unfavorable significance in patients with a focus in the left frontal lobe.

B-lymphocytes are thought to produce antibodies, and in this context may be regarded as a further stage of the immune process after recognition of antigens by T-lymphocytes (Amadori et al., 1995; Birnbaum, 1998; Daruna, 2004; Vedhara and Irvin, 2005). Based on our data it is suggested that high levels of B-lymphocytes in patients with a left frontal focus should be regarded as an indicator of overstrain of the cellular immune mechanism that has pro-convulsive effect on CPS. Principally, that for the right frontal focus such finding has not been obtained. Clearly, there is a connection between the left focus and the amount of B-lymphocytes.

Based on our data, the main conclusion is that the isolated immune variables except for CD4 count, as a rule, seem to be equivocally related to different seizure semiotics and data on CD4/CD8 ratio and CD8 cell values confirm this suggestion.

Sequences of seizures and immunity

Thus, a high CD4/CD8 index and a low CD8 value in patients with left-sided temporal focus and in females are associated with a low SPS frequency.

The principal question of the present study relates to the cause and sequence relationship between seizures and immunity. Obtained results are thought to be interpreted controversially, since low level of CD4/CD8 ratio in left temporal focus was related to high frequency of SPS, while the high count of B-lymphocytes was connected with high frequency of CPS. These data are difficult to explain.

From our point of view, suggestion can be made, that epileptic seizures can cause neuron destruction and subsequently an auto-antigen appearance that, in turn, can trigger an increase in CD4 cell levels, that lead to B-lymphocyte activation and finally to auto-antibodies production that, in turn, can result in further neuron destruction (Amadori et al., 1995; Birnbaum, 1998; Daruna, 2004; Vedhara and Irvin, 2005).

Thus so-called *circulus vitiosus* relationship between immune and neurobiological variables may evolve. Obviously, the optimal level of CD4 cells is required to reduce SPS frequency, while the hyper-production of CD4 cells can trigger further B-lymphocytes synthesis and they may interact with left frontal focus that can lead to increase of CPS frequency.

Interestingly none of the immune variables were observed to influence SGTCS frequency, and the reason for this needs to be identified.

Particular problems of remission and NK cells

A particular problem relates to the role of NK cells in sustaining of remission. In the present study only a trend to longer remission was identified in patients with left frontal focus and a high NK cell level ($p=0.08$). Nevertheless, this finding should not be ignored, since NK cells are thought to represent the innate unspecific immunity unlike the T-lymphocytes and B-lymphocytes (Amadori et al., 1995; Birnbaum, 1998; Daruna, 2004; Vedhara and Irvin, 2005). Obviously the frontal lobe epilepsy, with the left focus in particular, and low content of NK cells, represent the unfavorable form in terms of remission length, while the high level of NK cells depicts the preserved unspecific immunity.

A high CD4 cell level, on the other hand, seems to be correlated with a longer remission length irrespective of focus localization and focus lateralization and these findings supports a more complete role of specific immunity in the development of protective anti-epileptic mechanisms in comparison with the unspecific role of NK cells.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study has demonstrated that complex multifarious connections between neurobiological, immune and clinical variables in patients with partial forms of epilepsy really do exist, and they obviously should be taken into account. This may broaden our understanding of epilepsy pathogenesis and elaborate new approaches to prognosis and treatment.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DISCLOSURE

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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